

Speculation on Quantum Wavefunction Orthogonality and Quantization

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 23, 2024

In previous notes, we argued that free particle quantum mechanics arises from special relativity, in particular from the Lorentz invariant $A = -Et + px$ which is degenerate for $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$ where n is an integer. To obtain a probability function which respects the gradations for t and x , one needs periodicity, but also $P_1(p_1x)P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x)$. In other words, this is an indication of conservation of momentum. Here we suggest an alternative approach. The Lorentz invariant A describes different E and p values corresponding to frames moving with different constant $-v$ values. Hence, these are distinct frames. It is possible to accelerate free particles in one given frame to a set of different E, p 's. This means that a probability $P_1(px)$ should be distinct from $P_1(p_2x)$. We suggest that this requires orthogonality, i.e. $\int P_1^*(px) P_1(p_2x) dx = 0$ if p_2 is not p . One may note that there is no quantization here of p .

We further argue that for angular momentum or even bound state energy, the states are distinct and so the wavefunctions must be orthogonal as well. That does not imply quantization, we argue. Rather it is the presence of a non-uniform spatial density which causes quantization, we argue. For a bound state, we suggest that an infinitesimal change in E_n is equivalent to an infinitesimal change in $W_n(x)$ and that this cannot lead to an orthogonal function. A bound state is necessarily localized by definition.

For an eigenfunction of L and L_z , we argue that a spherical function yields $L_z W = L_x W = L_y W = 0$. Thus, to have angular momentum, one requires a localized function in θ . This localization, together with orthogonality leads to discrete $l(l+1)$ values for the LL operator.

The discrete m values, however, are more difficult to explain. A proof in (1) shows that the values $m = -L$ to $m = L$ in quantized steps of 1 follows from the commutation of relation of $[L_i, L_j]$. We suggest, however, that the constraint relation $[L_x, L_y] = i\hbar L_z$ shows L_z not noticing changes in probability because θ is constant, while L_x and L_y do. Thus, a lack of spherical symmetry in $P_l(\theta)$ (Legendre function) seems to be at the root of only some m values satisfying the constraint equation, whereas spherical symmetry (nonlocalization) would not have this issue it seems, but represents $l=0$ for the operator $L = r \times p$.

Wavefunction Orthogonality

We have argued in previous notes that free particle quantum mechanics follows from the Lorentz invariant: $A = -Et + px$ ((1)) because A is degenerate for $x = x_0 + n \cdot \hbar/p$ and $t = t_0 + n \cdot \hbar/E$, where n is an integer. This suggests gradations or resolution in space and time. If one were to have an associated probability function, one would expect the involvement of a periodic function which respects these resolutions. One way to find the probability, as noted in previous notes, is to use:

$$P_1(p_1x) P_1(p_2x) = P_1((p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((1))$$

Here we suggest a second way, which is essentially the same. We suggest that various E, p sets in special relativity are distinct as they are linked with frames moving with different constant $-v$ values. Thus, a $P_1(p_1x)$ and $P_2(p_2x)$ should be mutually exclusive, but they exist in the same x -space unlike event probabilities, e.g. the toss of a coin or roll of a die. This implies orthogonal functions, we argue:

$$\int P_1(p_1x) \cdot P_2(p_2x) dx = 0 \quad \text{for } p_1 \neq p_2 \quad ((2)) \quad (\text{one dimension})$$

We note that p is not quantized, i.e. any p value is allowed. Even though there are discrete \hbar/p units, any p value is allowed because $\exp(ipx)$'s are orthogonal.

Thus, in this section we try to establish the idea that the quantum probability (wavefunction) is orthogonal if the states are distinct.

Bound States

If the idea in the above section is correct, then one should have orthogonal $W_n(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ for a bound state and $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ for an angular momentum l, m state if these are indeed distinct. We argue that this has nothing to do with quantization at this point.

The question then becomes: How is a bound state or angular momentum state different from $\exp(ipx)$?

First, we wish to stress that $\exp(ipx)$ is a spatial probability describing p momentum hit probability in space, not motion. In other words, $x=vt$ and each x -point has the same weight and there is smooth motion. The momentum interaction, however, is not smooth and is based on a spatial probability $\exp(ipx)$. One may note, however, that $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$, i.e. this probability is not localized in space.

We suggest that the difference between $\exp(ipx)$ and $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ or $W_n(x)$ is that these others are localized in space. This means that $W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ is not a constant nor is $Y_{lm}^* Y_{lm}$. If one has localized interaction probability, we suggest that orthogonality of distinct states requires quantization.

As an example, consider the ground state of an oscillator. This consists of a single crest-like form and an energy $.5\hbar\omega$. If one were to try to change this energy infinitesimally, one might associate it with an infinitesimal change to the single crest-like form. An infinitesimal change, however, cannot lead to an orthogonal wavefunction which is required assuming the two states are distinct.

As a result, quantization seems to follow from orthogonality of distinct states (eigenfunctions) and localisation of interaction probability.

Angular Momentum States

Angular momentum requires two considerations, one for the magnitude of angular momentum and one for its projection on an axis, e.g. the z axis.

In the case of angular momentum, it is known that a spherical shape is associated with $L=0$, so one needs localization in space for an L . To see the localization, consider:

$$R_{xp} = (i)(y p_z - x p_y) - (j)(x p_z - z p_x) + (k)(x p_y - y p_x) \quad ((3))$$

If ((3)) operates on $W(x, y, z)$ one obtains 0. Thus one requires a breaking of spherical symmetry which we call localization, i.e. the preference of one theta over another.

Different L values are distinct, so given an L and a localized wavefunction, if one changes L infinitesimally, then the wavefunction changes infinitesimally and the two functions cannot be orthogonal. This is the same argument as used for a bound state and implies discrete, not continuous L values. (Formally, one considers eigenfunctions of $L \cdot L$ with $l(l+1)$ eigenvalues and $Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)$ eigenfunctions where Y_{lm} is proportional to $P_l(\cos(\theta)) \exp(im\phi)$ and P_l is a Legendre function.

Thus, we argue that the same type of argument used for a bound state, i.e. discrete E_n values for orthogonality, applies to eigenstates of LL . Changing l slightly leads to a slight change to the wavefunction and this cannot yield an orthogonal function.

A second consideration is the projection of L, say along the z-axis, i.e. m .

Thus, one may have rotation with $l(l+1)$ and a projection of L and another with $-L$, i.e. clockwise and counterclockwise rotations. The question now: Why cannot one have $\exp(im\phi)$ with any m value between $-l$ and l ? $\exp(im\phi)$ is like $\exp(ipx)$ in that $\exp(-im\phi) \exp(im\phi) = 1$ suggesting a uniform space at least in the sense of ϕ , while $P_l(\cos(\theta))$, the Legendre function does not treat space as uniform in the sense of θ , i.e. there is localization. If every m value were allowed for $\exp(im\phi)$ then this would imply that all of angular space were uniform, we argue, contradicting the nonuniformity dictated by $P_l(\cos(\theta))$.

We note that reference (1) proves that projection values m follow in steps of one from $-l$ to l , but this proof depends on the commutation relation:

$$[L_x, L_y] = i \hbar L_z \quad ((4))$$

We have shown that for $W(x, y, z)$, $L \cdot W = 0$, so for ((4)) to hold, one must have localization in space. If one considers L_x , L_y and L_z to be generators of rotation about the x, y and z directions, then it seems there is a geometrical interpretation for ((4)). L_z rotates about the z axis and there is uniform probability for ϕ , but not for θ , but it does not change. Rotations about x and y, however, notice this nonuniformity of θ and so lead to the commutation relation $[L_x, L_y]$ in the geometric interpretation. (Formally, it follows from using ((3)).) In particular, for a vector lying in the z-y plane and making an angle θ with the z axis, a rotation about the x-axis changes θ and leads to a different $P_l(\cos(\theta))$ value. Thus, a constraint equation ((4)) which does not allow for any m value of L_z is plausible due to the localization of $P_l(\cos(\theta))$. Non-discrete m values would seem to apply to a spherical function, but this has 0 angular momentum given r_{xp} with $p = -i \text{grad}$. Again, a formal proof is required for the discreteness of m and this is given in (1) using ((4)). We suggest that there is a geometrical reason as well. The constraint in ((4)) seen in terms of rotations about different axes only holds for discrete m values

and we suggest that this ultimately occurs because of the localization (non-spherical nature) of $P_l(\theta)$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that orthogonality of wavefunctions (probability) follows if one has distinct states (i.e. distinct eigenfunctions). This holds even if there is no quantization as in the case of $\exp(ipx)$ for which any p value is allowed.

We argue that in the case of localized wavefunctions in space, which occurs for bound states and $l(l+1)$ for an angular momentum state, orthogonality of distinct states requires discrete l or E_n values because an infinitesimal change in the wavefunction (assumed for an infinitesimal change in E_n or l) cannot lead to an orthogonal wavefunction.

We also suggest that this localization in space is the root reason for discrete m values in $\exp(im\phi)$, L_z eigenfunction values. The formal proof given in (1) using $[L_x, L_y] = i\hbar L_z$ may be thought of as a constraint equation with L_x , L_y and L_z being generators of rotation about the x, y, z direction. Even though L_z does not change θ , L_x could, for example, sense the change in θ and hence in the wavefunction, while L_z does not. Thus, the constraint seen in terms of rotations might only hold for certain m values, not all because of the localization of $P_l(\theta)$ where P_l is the Legendre function. A spherical function would seem to match a situation of all m values allowed, but a spherical function yields zero angular momentum using $r \times p$ with $p = -i \text{grad}$. Formally, one still needs to give a proof such as the one in (1), but we suggest that localization is at the root of it.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Angular_momentum_operator